

GEARS WITH INCOMPLETE TEETH

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ABSTRACT

In the article are presented transmissions in that the driving and driven tooth wheel rims are equipped with equal-height teeth of full and partial length, located along planar or spatial curves. Different types of these transmissions and speed variators are presented. Some kinematic parameters of these transmissions are calculated.

Keywords: gear transmissions, gear ratios, driving and driven wheels, teeth.

Modern machines are often required to implement the movement of actuators according to a given law of variable gear ratio.

To solve this problem, at present, gear transmissions with non-circular cylindrical wheels are used. Their disadvantage is considered to be high dynamic characteristics of the transmission, as well as the difficulties of manufacturing non-circular wheels.

To obtain a given law of variable gear ratio, it is possible to apply transmissions, the toothed rims of the driving and driven wheels of that are equipped with equal-height teeth of full and incomplete length, located along planar or spatial curves that represent a function of variable gear ratio.

Fig. 1. Bevel gear transmission

Fig. 2. Bevel gear

Fig. 3. Bevel gear with internal engagement

Fig. 4. Bevel disc-shaped circular transmission

Fig. 5. Bevel disc-shaped non-circular transmission

Gear transmissions (Fig. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) consist of driving 1 round bevel gears, and driven gears 2 are circular bevel gears (Fig. 1, 2, 3), or disk-shaped circular (Fig. 4) or disk-shaped non-circular (Fig. 5). The toothed rims of the driving and driven gears are equipped with equal-height straight teeth of full 3 and incomplete 4 length, external (Fig. 1, 2, 4, 5) and internal (Fig. 3) engagement. Incomplete teeth are located along spatial and plane curves 5, which represent a given function of the variable gear ratio. The vertices of the cones in the plan are located on the generatrix and are shifted from each other by a distance "a".

The gear ratios for the gears (Fig. 1, 2, 3) are determined by the dependencies:

$$U_{\max} = \frac{L_{e2} \sin \delta_2}{(L_{e2} \pm a) \sin \delta_1}; \quad (1)$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{L_{i2} \sin \delta_2}{(L_{i2} \pm a) \sin \delta_1};$$

For transmission (Fig. 4)

$$U_{\max} = \frac{L_{e2}}{(L_{e2} \pm a) \sin \delta_1}; \quad (2)$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{L_{i2}}{(L_{i1} \pm a) \sin \delta_1};$$

And for the transmission (Fig. 5) will be as

$$U_{\max} = \frac{R_{e2max}}{(R_{e2max} - a) \sin \delta_1}; \quad (3)$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{R_{i2min}}{(R_{i2min} - a) \sin \delta_1};$$

When the teeth of gear 2 (Fig.5) is located on the ellipse

$$U_{\max} = \frac{A(1 - e^2)}{1 - e}; \quad (4)$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{A(e^2 - 1)}{1 + e};$$

where R_{e2} – is the external cone radius of gear 2; R_{i2} – is the internal cone radius of gear 2; R_{i1} – is the internal cone radius of gear 1; δ_1, δ_2 - are the reference angles of gears 1,2; A- is the half length of ellipse major axis; e- eccentricity of ellipse.

The minus sign refers to the case when the vertex O_1 of the driving wheel 1 is located on the generatrix of the driven wheel 2, and the plus sign refers to the case when the vertex O_2 of the driven wheel 2 is located on the generatrix of the driving wheel.

The adjustment range for gears (Fig. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) is as follows

$$D = \frac{L_{e2}(L_{i2} \pm a)}{L_{i2}(L_{e2} \pm a)}. \quad (5)$$

For transmission (Fig.5) when the teeth of gears 2 are located on the ellipse

$$D = \frac{1 + e}{1 - e}. \quad (6)$$

For the presented cases, the plus sign applies to Fig. 1, 4, and the minus sign applies to Fig. 2, 3, 5.

The gear transmissions (Fig. 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11) consist of driving spherical (Fig. 6, 7, 8, 9, 10) and ellipsoidal (Fig. 11) gears 1 and driven spherical (Fig. 6, 7, 8) internal engagement and toroidal (Fig. 9, 10, 11) external engagement gears 2. The driving 1 and driven 2 gears toothed rims are equipped with equal-height straight (Fig. 6, 7, 9, 10, 11) or helical (Fig. 8) teeth of full 3 and incomplete 4 length and are located along spatial curves 5, which represent a given function of the variable (Fig. 6, 7, 8, 9, 10), or variable-constant (Fig.

11) gear ratios. The gear axes are located in relation to each other: parallel (Fig. 6), at an angle (Fig. 8) or intersecting (Fig. 7, 9, 10, 11).

Fig. 6. Transmission with spherical gears

Fig. 7. Transmission with spherical gears

Fig. 8. Transmission with spherical gears

The gear ratios for the gears (Fig. 6, 7, 8) are as follows:

$$U_{\max} = \frac{R_{2\max}}{R_{1\max}}; \tag{7}$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{R_{2\min}}{R_{1\min}}$$

The adjusting range or gear ratio is

$$D = \frac{R_{2\max} \cdot R_{1\min}}{R_{1\max} \cdot R_{2\min}}$$

The gear ratios and adjusting range of gear ratio for transmission (Fig. 9 and 11) will be as

$$U_{\max} = \frac{R_{2\max}}{R_1};$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{R_{2\min}}{R_{1\min}}. \tag{8}$$

$$D = \frac{R_{2\max} \cdot R_{1\min}}{R_1 \cdot R_{2\min}}$$

For transmission (Fig. 10)

$$U_{\max} = \frac{R_{2\min}}{R_1 - r_1}; \tag{9}$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{R_{2\max}}{R_1};$$

$$D = \frac{R_{2\max} \cdot (R_1 - r_1)}{R_1 \cdot R_{2\min}}$$

Fig.9. Transmission with spherical and gears

Fig. 10. Transmission with spherical and toroidal gears

Let's consider the case of using such transmissions in variators. A four-speed variator (Fig. 12) consists of a driving 1, intermediate 2, 3, driven 4 toroidal gears and intermediate spherical or elliptical gears 5, 6 that are connected with the fixed axle 7 with the possibility of free rotation. Gears 1, 2, 6 are equipped with equally high straight teeth 8 of incomplete length that are located along the same or different spatial curves 9, 10, 11, which represent a given function of the variable gear ratio. Wheels 3, 4, 5 are equipped with equally high straight teeth 12 of full length. Wheels 2, 3 are

Fig. 11. Transmission with ellipsoidal and toroidal gears

connected to each other by shafts 13, 14, 15 and round bevel wheels 16, 17, 18, 19.

The gear ratio function is determined by the dependencies:

$$U_{\max} = \frac{r_{2\max} \cdot r_{4\max} \cdot R_{5\min} \cdot R_{6\min}}{r_{1\min} \cdot r_{3\min} \cdot R_{5\max} \cdot R_{6\max}},$$

$$U_{\min} = \frac{r_{2\min} \cdot r_{4\min} \cdot R_{5\max} \cdot R_{6\max}}{r_{1\max} \cdot r_{3\max} \cdot R_{5\min} \cdot R_{6\min}}. \quad (10)$$

Fig. 12. Four-stage speed variator

Adjusting range of gear ratio

$$D = \frac{r_{1\max} \cdot r_{2\max} \cdot r_{3\max} \cdot r_{4\max} \cdot R_{5\min}^2 \cdot R_{6\min}^2}{r_{1\min} \cdot r_{2\min} \cdot r_{3\min} \cdot r_{4\min} \cdot R_{5\max}^2 \cdot R_{6\max}^2}$$

If it is necessary for the driven wheels and transmission shafts to rotate with different gear ratio laws, then the incomplete-length teeth must be located along different curves that represent different functions of the given variable gear ratio law. The curve composed of

parts corresponding to different functions of the variable gear ratio is located on the initial surface of the driving or driven gears.

The calculation of the main kinematic parameters of the variator gear wheels would be carried out according to the specified parameters, when $\varphi_2 = \varphi_3 = \varphi_{12} = \varphi_5 = \varphi_6 = 62^\circ$; $R_2 = R_5 = 190\text{mm}$; $R_3 = 140\text{mm}$; $R_6 = 150\text{mm}$.

Results of the kinematic parameters calculation

Title	$r_{1\min}$	$r_{1\max}$	$r_{2\min}$	$r_{2\max}$	$r_{3\min}$	$r_{3\max}$	$r_{4\min}$	$r_{4\max}$	U_{\min}	U_{\max}	D
Four-stage variator	55	225	45	220	45	185	45	185	0,193	5,209	27,35

Thus, the conducted research made it possible to significantly simplify the process of manufacturing gear transmissions using standard serial equipment and to increase the range of change of the gear ratio and the efficiency of the speed variator transmission.

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